

A Contextual Analysis of Election of the Deacons in Acts 6:1-7: An Insight for National Integration

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Abstract

Nigerians today confront a number of problems ranging from economic malaise, social disintegration, political intolerance, ethnic discrimination, gross violation of human rights, insecurity and abject poverty amidst plenty. While 10% of the population is living in unprecedented affluence, majority of the rest is condemned to poverty, to some kind of oppression, deprivation and discrimination. The painful awareness that the present self-inflicted economic depression alarmingly increases their number day by day and the fact that the situation of the millions of Nigerians is worsening to a dangerous level of survival calls for urgent attention by all concerned especially, the religious leaders of this nation. This paper examines the election of the Deacons in Acts 6:1-8 as an insight for National integration. The aim is to appraise the process of election and electoral system within a Christian paradigm, to relate it to current democratic practices in Nigerian society. To achieve these tasks, the paper employs the descriptive, hermeneutical and exegetical methods. The Finding reveals that many political office holders misunderstood and abused the political authority for their selfish interest. The paper concludes that the biblical principles and practices are ideal pattern that can guarantee all-inclusiveness, equal representation and good governance; it therefore recommends that leaders should have the fear of God and respect for fundamental human right of every citizen when they occupy the position of authority.

Keywords: Election, Governance, National integration, Political process.

Introduction

The church is a pluralistic community where people of different races and languages were represented, but the dominant groups were the Jews who were Hebrew speaking Christians and the Greek-born Jews whose lingua franca was Greek. Consequently, a new factor entered into the history of the church. The narrative begins with a criticism of the arrangement of the distribution of the community's wealth among the needy. The membership of the church had become so large and complex that the twelve could no longer cope adequately with the management and distribution of the community's wealth. When the problem came to the head seven administrator was appointed.¹ According to Luke it was Hellenistic Jewish Christians that lodged a complaint that the Hebrew speaking Christian widows received more attention than the Hellenistic widows in the daily distribution of the common property. Many Hellenistic Jews who were born abroad sometimes came to settle in Jerusalem where they had several synagogues. Christianity had won a large number of converts from among them. Their widows were probably relatively large because many pious Jews in the evening of their days came to settle in Jerusalem so as to be buried near the holy city. The widow of such men had no relative to care for them and therefore became dependent on public charity.²

Among the Jews, every Friday two or three relief officers went round markets and houses to collect donations for the poor in cash and in kinds. Therefore, weekly provision for fourteen meals in cash and kind was distributed to the poor. The money was first collected in the box by relief officers. The collection for the poor was therefore called *Qupah* (box or basket). There was also an arrangement for the daily collection of food from house to house in order to meet cases of emergency for the poor strangers and those who were temporarily resident in the city. The daily collection and distribution of food and drink from the tray gave this daily offering the name *Tha mahu* (tray). The function of the deacons in the primitive church was similar to what obtained in the Jewish communities. But obviously, the Christians introduced a system of poor-relief quite distinct from the Jews,³ the Apostles recommended the appointment of seven men as administrators of the community's wealth. The seven men were to be men of proven integrity, men of good reputation, full of the spirit and wisdom. The Apostles did not just hand pick the seven men but they were chosen by the community and were later commissioned by the Apostles. This possibly had some connection with a Jewish institution. In every local Jewish community, they had a local council made up of seven men known as the "seven of the Town" or the "Seven best of the Town."⁴ The quick intervention by the Apostles, as well as their wisdom and sense of justice kept the primitive church together as a united body. The early Christians took their social responsibility very seriously. The need of the community

was the concern of every member and the need of an individual was the responsibility of the whole group. Blessed are those widows whose complaints had helped the early church to be alive to its social obligations to all and sundry.⁵

Leadership Challenges in Nigeria

Leadership is the lubricant of development of a nation or of any organization, from time immemorial leadership has been offered at different levels. In the Pentateuch, Yahweh is the leader of His people, He exercises this through morals. Leadership has been defined in various ways and each scholar tends to favour a definition which agrees with his set goals. Political leadership is one of the various categories of leadership. Morell and Hartley opined that leaders are democratically elected representatives who are vulnerable to deselection, and operate within, as well as influence, a constitutional and legal framework; their source of authority is a mandate given by the electorate. Political leaders bear the responsibility of managing the affairs and resources of an independent political entity.⁶ Ejimabo Nathaniel pointed out that most of the public office holders in Nigeria are people who have not shown the capacity for leadership but have manipulated the people and their ways into various leadership positions through corrupted electoral processes. As such, Nigerian society has remained pauperised and the people wallowing in abject poverty. Political leaders are supposed to harness and maximize the available resources of the country for greatest good of the people.⁷

Political leadership in Nigeria has been an unfortunate one where the entire problem of the Nation has been summarized as leadership failure. Political leadership in Nigeria used power to its advantage rather than that of the people. The question of political leaders shortchanging the electoral masses by saying one thing and doing another is one of the issues on the front burner of the complex spectrum of political integrity. Other issues on this wide spectrum of integrity in political leadership are outright corruption such as overt and covert bribe, political donations and lobbying, buying access to political power or positions, disclosure of funds raised and donors during political campaign, among others.⁸

The Grek Text of Acts 6:1-7

1. Ἐν δε ταῖς ἡμέραις ταυταῖς πληθυνοντων των μαθητων ἐγένετο γογγυσμός των Ἑλληνιστων προστούς Ἑβραίους ὅτι παρεθεωρουντο εν τῇ διάκονια τῇ καθημερινη αἰ χηραι αὐτων.
2. Προσκαλεσάμενοι δέ οἱ δώδεκα τό πλήθος των μαθητων εἶπαν. Ὅυκ ἀρεστόν ἐστιν ἡμάς καταλείψαντας τόν λόγον του θεοῦ διακονεῖν τραπέζαις.
3. Ἐπισκέψασθε δέ ἀδελφοί, ἀνδρας ἐξ ὑμῶν μαρτυρουμένους ἐπτά πλήρεις πνεύματος και σοφίας οὓς καταστήσομεν ἐπί τῆς χρείας ταύτης,
4. Ἡμεῖς δέ τῇ προσευχῇ και τῇ διάκονια του λόγου προσκαρτερήσομεν.
5. Και ἠρεσεν ὁ λόγος ἐνώπιόν παντος του πλήθους και ἐξελέξαντο Στεφανον, ανδρα πλήρης πίστεως και πνεύματος αγίου, και Φίλιππον και Πρόχορον και Νικάνορα και Τίμωνα Παρμενάν και Νικόλαον προσήλυτον Ἀντιοχέα,
6. Οὓς ἐστήσαν ἐνώπιον των ἀποστόλων, και προσευξάμενοι ἐπέθηκαν αὐτοῖς τὰς χεῖρας.
7. Και ὁ λόγος του θεου ἠύξανεν και ἐπληθύνετο ὁ ὄγλος των μαθητων ἐν Ἱερουσαλήμ σφόδρα, πολὺς τε ὄγλος των ἱερέων ὑπήκουον τῇ πίστει.

Translation

1. At this time, as the disciples were increasing in number, a complaint was voiced by the Hellenists against the Hebrews, because their widows were being over looked at the daily distribution
2. Then the twelve called the whole body of the disciples to the and said, It is not desirable that we should leave (the ministry of) the word of God and serve at the tables
3. So, brothers, look out seven men from your number, men of good repute, full of the Spirit and wisdom, whom we may put in charge of this business.
4. We ourselves will continue in prayer and in the ministry of the word.
5. What they said was approved by the whole company, so they chose Stephen, a man full of faith and the Holy Spirit, Philip, Prochorus, Nicanor, Timon, Permenas, and Nicholas, a proselyte from Antioch.

6. They brought these men before the Apostles, who prayed and laid their hands on them.
7. The word of God advanced and the number of the disciples in Jerusalem increased greatly; moreover, a large company of the priests were rendering obedience to the faith

Exegetical Analysis of Acts 6:1-7

The time has now come to record a new and momentous advance in the life of the new community. This advance involved the large-scale evangelization of the Gentiles. It was the Hellenists, Ἑλληνισταὶ in the church who took the lead in this enterprise, and as they have not been mentioned in the record thus far, Luke introduces his account of it by saying something about them and their leaders.⁹ The church of Jerusalem, comprised both “Hebrews” and “Hellenists.” The main distinction the two groups were Greek and who attended Greek-speaking synagogues; the Hebrews spoke Aramaic (or Mishnaic Hebrew) and attended synagogues where the service was concluded in Hebrew. Many of the Hellenists had affinities with the lands of the Jewish dispersion around the Mediterranean shores, whereas the Hebrew were Palestinian Jews; there were doubtless several minor social and cultural differences between the two groups. In the Jewish world as a whole there were tensions between them and some of these tensions endured between members of the two groups who had joined the “disciples” as the followers of Jesus are here called for the first time in Acts.¹⁰

It was a practical issue, and not over a matter of theological importance, that disagreement became acute. As daily allocations were made to poorer members of the community from the common fund to which the wealthier members had contributed their property, complaints began to arise that one group was being favored at the expense of the other. Widows naturally formed a considerable proportion of the poor members of the church, and the Hellenistic widows were said to be at a disadvantage in comparison with the Hebrew widows, perhaps because the distribution of charity was in the hands of the “Hebrews.”¹¹

The Apostles or “the Twelve” as they were called here wisely determined to put the trouble right at once. It was not their primary business to supervise the financial arrangement of the community or to take an active part in the *daylie handreachinge* (as Coverdale’s English version of 1535 calls it). They therefore called the community together and bade them select seven men to be responsible for administering the charitable allocation.¹² These seven should be men of honorable reputation, so that their probity might command complete confidence; they should be wise men, competent in administration and also qualified to deal wisely with a situation in which such delicate human susceptibilities had to be considered; above all, they must be men of God, filled with his Spirit. This might be regarded as ideal requirements for all the church appointments. If such men could be found, to take charge of the distribution and see that no further cause for justified complaint arose, the apostles would be free to devote their undistracted attention to directing the church’s regular worship and to preaching the gospel.¹³

The apostles’ suggestion was approved, and seven men were selected in verse 5. All seven appear to have been Hellenists; indeed, they were probably the recognized leaders of the Hellenists in the church. Stephen is more particularly described as “a man full of faith and the Holy Spirit”. Phillip also plays an important part in the subsequent narrative of Acts. About the other five Luke has nothing further to say Prochorus is represented in the later tradition as being an attendance of John the evangelist, as bishop of Nicomedia, and as martyred at Antioch. About Nicolaus, the last-named of the seven, two interesting facts are mentioned: he was not even a Jew by birth, but a proselyte (a convert to Judaism from paganism), and he belongs to Antioch on the Orontes.¹⁴ As earlier as the time of Irenaeus (A.D 180), and possibly earlier, this Nicolaus was held to be the founder of the party of the Nicolaitans, who received unfavorable mention in Rev.2:6, 15. The Nicolaitans certainly derived their name from some Nicolaus-whether from this Nicolaus or another must remain uncertain.¹⁵

Importantly, it was the community as whole that selected these seven men and presented them to the apostles for their approbation; it was the apostles who installed them in office. They did not lay hands on them, after prayer. The imposition of hands is mentioned in a variety of contexts in Old Testament for the bestowal of a blessing (Gen. 48:13-20), for expressing identification, as when the sacrificial victim (Lev.1:4; 3:2;4:4;16:21), for commissioning a successor (Num.27:23), and so forth. According to the Mishnah, members of the Sanhedrin were admitted by the imposition of hands. In the present instance the imposition of the apostolic hands formally associated the Twelve with the appointment of the Seven to discharge their special duties. It did not, of course, impart the gift of the Spirit; the Seven were already “full of the Spirit” (v.3).¹⁶

The Seven have conventionally been called “deacons,” in a number of Christian traditions this designation has come to be used in a restricted sense of those who are responsible for the financial affairs of the church. While the Greek noun *διακονος*, from which “deacon” is derived, is not used in this passage, the related word *διακονεω* is used (which means to “serve,” in v.2); but *διακονια* is used partially of the daily “distribution” (v.1) and the “ministry” of preaching (v.4).¹⁷

While the Seven were appointed to service as deacons, it is plain that their activity were confirmed by their diligence and dedication. Stephen and Philip, at any rate, were well equipped for the public leadership in general and for the particular forms of service in when Luke describes them as engaging-Stephen for the defense of the gospel and Philip for the work of evangelism.¹⁸ The progress report was the focus of verse seven; at this point Luke interrupts his narrative with a brief report of progress. Six of such reports appear at intervals throughout Acts and serve to punctuate the history. But here, immediately before the account of Stephen’s activity, there is special relevance in Luke’s emphasis on the church’s increase in numbers and popularity. In particular, the fact that so many priests were joining the community meant that the ties which attached many of the believers to the temple order would be strengthened. It is not suggested that these priests relinquished their priestly office; the logic of such a step would not be generally appreciated at this stage¹⁹ the ordinary priests were socially and in other ways far removed from the wealthy chief-priestly families from which main opposition to the gospel came. Many of the ordinary priests were no doubt holy men and humble of heart, like Zechariah, father of the John the Baptist, men who would readily be persuaded of the truth of the gospel. But it was not good that the new movement should be too closely attached to the old order, and there is ‘tremendous tension’ in the juxtaposition of the reference to these priests and the account of Stephen’s insistence that the temple order was now superseded.

Election of Deacons in Nigerian Context

The early community exhibited Christian virtues, especially love expressed in the sharing of material goods as discussed above has no trace of any compulsion in the sharing of private property, but Christians were willing to share their material goods. Consequently, none of the Christian was impoverished. The properties of the converts did not immediately after conversion become the possessions of the corporate visible church but these properties were freely released for sale from time to time and the proceeds brought to the apostles to meet the needs of the poor and needy.¹⁹ The origin of the early community may be traced to Jesus and his disciples and in the contagious joy of new life in Jesus and of a common life in the Spirit, overflowing into a sharing of wealth. However, this earliest manifestations of fellowship, devotion, and provision for the poor was not an economic programme, but an expression of worship and the central concern of all members.²⁰

Therefore, the modern vision for the society where the needs of all are met by the sharing of common wealth among all and sundry has been part and parcel of Christianity from the beginning. Nevertheless, it is different from communism which in modern usage refers to any economic scheme which advocates common ownership of property, but which in actual life situation has not been absolutely practicable. Communism refers not to a religiously motivated renunciation of private property but rather to a kind of political programme and ideology. While Christianity aims at achieving its goals through voluntary devotion to common ideals of brotherhood and neighbourliness.²¹

Furthermore, the need for a just society cannot be overemphasized, a society that will ultimately lead to a just economic programme for the common good of all. The primary significance of justice is its tendency to counteract the crude egoism of the individual or a group of individuals. As regard the good things of life, the egoist philosophy is ‘everything for me’ or ‘for my tribe’ regardless of whether or not anything remains for the others. Against this justice maintains: “not everything for me but the same thing for me and others”. Justice acts as a check against all grievous sinning against one’s fellowman, whether against body, life, property, social status, reputation or honour. The essential feature in justice is equality. Those who practice injustice in political and economic power sharing, especially the common wealth are criminals who deny themselves and others the legal basis upon which they themselves and others rest.²²

One cannot discuss the election of deacons among the community of goods and just society of equal opportunities without commenting on the issue of quota system in Nigeria. One must agree that this is unavoidable in some areas of life in Nigeria. But it becomes a serious moral issue when competence, experience, excellence, the technical-know-how and academic qualifications are all sacrificed on the altar of quota system.²³ This will continue to affect Nigerian’s effort to develop and catch up technologically with the rest of the developed countries of the world. Quota system in Nigeria is apparently an indirect way of stepping down the rate of development in certain parts of the country until the other parts are able to catch up with them. The bitter truth is that both objectives cannot be achieved through the present quota system which is a big threat to our national unity.²⁴

The need for selfless leaders in the country is the lasting solution to the problem of the poor sharing of the national wealth, the bridging of the gap between the rich and the poor, corruption, tribalism, etc. lies in the rise of truly patriotic national leaders in Nigeria whose approach to national issues would rise above tribal considerations or the question of the state of origin or the interest of the former political regions of Nigeria.²⁵ Most of the past and even the present leaders were often driven by greed and political ambition and were therefore unable to see themselves as servant of the entire nation, having the responsibility to look after the welfare of the entire nation without discrimination. Our leaders often put self above the nation. Nigeria since independence has been in search of a truly dedicated national leadership, and this is a matter for great concern.²⁶

The community of good in the Acts 6:1-7 were concerned about the type of leaders that would be in charge of the community goods. They must be men of good reputation, full of wisdom, godly and full of Holy Spirit. Surprisingly all the men were chosen from only one of two major tribes in the early church. There was no quota system in the choice of leadership²⁷ what were important to the early community of goods were honesty, dedication, godliness and ability to serve. The election of the seven dedicated able leaders put an end to all misunderstanding and this saved the church from distinction²⁸ It was in consequence of the universalistic spirit of these seven leaders that the gospel message spread beyond the confines of Judea to the rest of Palestine and later to the uttermost ends of the earth. This is how Christianity became a universal religion and why it did not die a natural death like other new sect within Judaism.²⁹

The problem with Nigeria is that she had in the past been ruled by many Ananias and Sapphira. These were rogues-turned saints overnight after assuming political authority or the few Nigerians who stole away the national wealth in their private bank accounts abroad, while Nigeria is at verge of economic collapse. Nigeria had had more of pretenders rather than truly dedicated national leaders as rulers who suddenly became millionaires and billionaires like Ananias and Sapphira, nemesis will sooner or later catch up with all the Nigerian rogues-turned-saints.³⁰ Nigeria did not need dictatorship, but national leaders with the fear of God, proven honesty and integrity.³¹ Leaders whose leadership would not depend on the place of birth, religion, state or tribe, profession but on the leadership qualities and nationalistic spirit which they possess. Nigeria is blessed with huge natural resources, many of which are yet to be tapped, apart from the vast land for agriculture. What is crucial now is the proper management and utilization of all our resources for the common good of all Nigerians and not just for the benefit of the few privileged ones as it is still the case today.³²

Conclusion

The Christian concern is with men everywhere, no matter their religion, economic conditions, ethnic affiliations etc. economic and political justice is inseparable. The church in Nigeria, therefore, has mission not only to Christian but to the country as a whole³³ the church must continue to preach Jesus Christ and love which manifests itself in justice towards all without discrimination, just political and economic structures and a just sharing of our national wealth³⁴ All-inclusive administration must be encouraged at all levels of governance, where everybody will be represented and well catered for in the scheme of things. The future destiny of the nation hangs on social justice administered by national leaders who are of good reputation, good character, integrity, full of wisdom, godly and filled with the Spirit of God.³⁵

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